

Continuous eHealth monitoring ecosystem for bronchial asthma and air quality

eHME, Continuous eHealth Monitoring Ecosystem

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ABSTRACT

Scientific literature has consistently identified links between bad air quality and the worsening of bronchial asthma symptomatology. To keep track of it individually, recent technology advances point to the potential benefits of using Internet of Medical Things technologies for the monitoring of respiratory health conditions. This paper describes an eHealth Monitoring Ecosystem developed for bronchial asthmatic supervision with the purpose of promoting patients' well-being, air quality awareness and potential links between symptoms and individual exposure to pollutants. Physiology and air quality data will be collected by means of wearable devices, facilitating an individualized assessment during a piloting phase that includes clinical supervision. This ecosystem is designed to include user-friendly interfaces for both patients and healthcare professionals which will ultimately serve to better understand the individualized clinical case of an asthmatic patient, especially sensitive to air pollution given the existing health condition.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Applied computing** → Health care information systems; • **Information systems** → Information systems applications; Decision support systems.

KEYWORDS

air quality, wearables, IoT, eHealth, asthma, machine learning

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1 INTRODUCTION

Scientific evidence points to the fact that bronchial asthmatic patient's quality of life significantly decreases when exposure to bad air quality takes place for short and long-term [6, 7]. Although previous studies on respiratory health and air quality using general meteorological stations have been performed with significant clinical results [7], current eHealth strategies and technologies allow the patient's monitoring to become more individualized and accurate than those using general atmospheric data [2]. The rise of the Internet of Things (IoT) could support the transition to remote monitoring contexts. More specifically, Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) technologies [11] together with wearable devices [8] can be used to continuously supervise both the health state of the asthmatic patient and, in parallel, the air quality they are individually exposed to, in order to generate databases to perform machine learning (ML) techniques from which healthcare personnel and the health system as a whole could benefit from [4]. Research based on mobile phone platforms and wearables already proved technology deployment feasible for the control of asthma in pediatric patients [5]. Current expertise in unsupervised ML for elucidating existent patterns in health data, as exemplified in cardiac health challenges [3], has the potential to be integrated in IoT platforms for relevant analysis in health. Similarly, supervised ML approaches to physiology data processing [1, 9, 10] have been extensively used for the identification of predefined conditions that compromise health in multiple domains suitable for wearable tracking. In an interdisciplinary project between pneumology experts and IoT developers, we propose to use innovative personalized monitoring technologies to create a whole "asthma and air quality eHealth monitoring ecosystem (eHME)" in the form of a digital platform for patients and healthcare professionals so that the bronchial asthmatic patient's quality of life can ultimately improve. With an early

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feasibility study based on eHME and under the coordination of a pneumology team, we expect that links between exposure to certain air pollutants and asthma symptomatology worsening can be better understood in an individualized manner.

2 OBJECTIVE

Our research seeks a smart eHealth monitoring system for bronchial asthma patients, potentially benefiting patients' wellbeing. This system must articulate the integration of regular, remote, data acquisition of asthma symptoms and progression, air quality with individual exposure to particular air pollutants and clinical supervision. Specific non-invasive tools are used to monitor the bronchial asthmatic patient in a non-disturbing manner, which are part of the eHealth ecosystem. The eHME (Figure 1) consists of three wearable devices and an eHealth platform, i.e., a web/app interface showing integrated information and analytics hosted in the cloud. The eHealth platform will also enable an active clinical rapport and variable acquisition through questionnaires and forms that require manual input. In order to advance into an improved wellbeing of the asthma patients, we have outlined the following objectives:

- Create an eHME for bronchial asthmatic patients and air quality based on cutting-edge sensing technologies, wearable innocuous sensors and IoT deployment strategies leveraging AI data analysis.
- Integrate this eHealth ecosystem into the regular clinical pneumology supervision practice, enhancing a beneficial user experience for both the asthmatic patient and the personalized pneumology care in general in order to improve diagnosis, treatment, follow-up and prevention of individualized cases of bronchial asthmatic patients in a potentially problematic air quality context.

3 METHODOLOGY

The development of the eHME involves ecosystem design and testing, alongside a two-stage (pre-clinical/clinical) early feasibility study in a clinical domain.

3.1 The eHealth Monitoring Ecosystem (eHME).

Specific non-invasive tools are used to monitor the bronchial asthmatic patient in a non-disturbing manner, which are part of the eHealth ecosystem. The eHME (Figure 1) consists of three wearable devices and an eHealth platform, i.e., a web/app interface showing integrated information and analytics hosted in the cloud. The eHealth platform will also enable an active clinical rapport and variable acquisition through questionnaires and forms that require manual input.

The wearable devices are:

- FitBit®sense Smartwatch for monitoring state of health: heart rate (bpm), SpO2 (blood oxygen saturation %) and breathing rate estimation among others.
- Small portable air quality sensor Flow2®: NO2 and PM2.5 particulate matter concentration metrics (ppb, $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}^3$), alongside local environmental variables such as temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and relative humidity (%).
- CapMedic®: Smart inhaler cap for FEV1(liter) and PEF(liters/min) lung function measurements (forced

expiratory volume in 1 second and peak expiratory flow, respectively) and for acute asthma episode tracking (rescue medication intake).

Devices will be where the patient is at all times, collecting objective data 24/7. Databases of raw data capturing the different measurement aspects will be gathered. Data will flow from the devices to an IoMT cloud where integration and processing are to be applied, forwarding detailed insights onto the digital platform – smartphone app / computer clinical program. Unsupervised ML techniques will be applied during the clinical study in order to uncover existing associations between measurements. In turn, detailed analysis using supervised ML will help establish useful answers for the patients regarding their asthma and the air quality they are exposed to, so that their individual case can be better understood by the healthcare professionals and/or their worsening health status (e.g., exacerbation) could be predicted.

The eHME is devised as an ecosystem to complement clinical supervision of asthma. This means that the ecosystem extends information with objective and personalized metrics otherwise out of reach of the clinical teams. For privacy-preserving purposes, the system assigns a unique ID code to each user, anonymizing user identity details and not storing any sensitive data, by design. Personalized air quality and physiology metrics are combined on a day to day basis, always referred to the assigned ID. Hospital General Parc Sanitari Sant Joan de Déu's ethics committee guarantees data privacy and security compliance at any step of the data flow, ensuring personal data is only hosted at the Hospital premises (and not within the system), and that accessible metrics to correlate are fully anonymized.

3.2 Pre-clinic

User-friendly access to relevant data is essential in the development and design of the digital IoT platform. These data will take the final shape of post-processed data highlighting relevant respiratory health traits after ML techniques and filtering have been applied to the raw data collected by wearable devices.

Collaborations with wearable device manufacturers and the identification of accurate commercial products are already in line to ensure reliable access to high quality data. The IoT team is in charge of the overall data flow covering stages from raw data collected by the devices to processed and relevant data insights delivered on the digital platform for the patients/clinicians.

On the other hand, during pre-clinical stage, the eHME is tested on 5 volunteers in order to verify its suitability in a real scenario, with the purpose of highlighting redundant functionalities to be discarded or, on the contrary, enabling the addition of new ones. These volunteers wear the devices for 2 weeks and a daily examination of the technical and behavioral details are performed, such as: data flow from the devices to the app, visualization of data on the app, any inconvenience during the setup process, volunteer's adaptation to the devices, adherence, and comfort as subject of the study – important for avoiding undesired study dropouts. Opinion and suggestion surveys are distributed during test execution and upon completion. A detailed report is finally generated covering any technical, clinical, or behavioral complication experienced during the testing phase with the 5 volunteers.

Figure 1: eHME schematic. Data will be collected by the three wearables: Fitbit®, Flow2® and CapMedic® and sent to the IoT cloud where it will be integrated. Useful information will be shown then in an intuitive eHealth platform app for both patients and healthcare professionals.

3.3 Clinical study

Once eHME tests conclude, pneumologists will recruit suitable participants among asthma patients undergoing regular symptom supervision, offering voluntary study participation to those who are suitable according to inclusion and exclusion requirements that ensure an adequate sample. Upon information session conclusion and informed consent signature, an eHME kit, including the three different devices, is given to each participant, launching a continuous remote monitoring experience that will last for six months. Whole professional coverage in patient’s support and guidance will be offered in order to minimize inconveniences or disturbances caused by the study and to ensure that data collection is guaranteed.

A total of 25 patients will be monitored, collecting data on a minute-basis for several variables - being the main ones: heart rate, SpO₂, NO₂ and PM_{2.5}, - resulting in databases where ML techniques will be performed.

Therefore, the proposed early feasibility study, will have two main outcomes.

- Mathematical models created to assist, monitor, and prevent adverse situations in bronchial asthmatic patients.
- eHME improved and strengthened as a healthcare tool, not only as a digital technological system but also as a useful monitoring platform for the pneumological clinical practice, by means of:
- Gathered data on perceived subjective experience via feedback forms during study execution.

- Daily questionnaires gathering subjective data about asthma status and self-perceived health.

At the end of the study, we expect the eHME to be fully outlined and the models to work successfully, being applicable to a use case scenario in a clinical context.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has introduced the development of an IoMT eHealth monitoring system, uniquely integrating wearables’ data on personalized physiology and air quality to be applied in bronchial asthma supervision. Currently, tests with eHME have been successfully performed with 5 initial volunteers, achieving promising outcomes, while battery usage for the multiple devices and smartphone, data synchronization and app communication permissions have emerged as a significant challenge from the user perspective. The eHME has proven to work as planned. Storage, data flow and responses are fully functional. With a clearly designed early feasibility study in a clinical domain, future steps in the following months consist of applying the eHME in a clinical context with the involvement of patients and healthcare professionals. Experiences gathered during the study and current data integration/processing mechanisms will be used to continuously improve the eHME and the ML techniques utilized. Despite the design has been developed looking towards clinical applications, the R&D team has identified

the potential to further develop the eHME as a product for a combined air quality exposure and physiology tracking in a personalized manner.

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